

THE ROLE OF LATIN LANGUAGE IN THE WORLD STATEHOOD

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ABSTRACT

Roman literature is a rich cultural heritage for the peoples of the world. One of them is winged words, literary quotes, figurative expressions and proverbs. We know and are well aware that the use of appropriate proverbs in our speech can give the effect and eloquence of our speech. Also, Latin is a medical language. All terms related to this field are studied in this language. This language is widely taught in medical schools. The goal of this course is to teach future medical workers skills, such as independent reading in Latin and understanding medical texts with the help of a dictionary, learning information from local scientific literature and writing in their field, diagnosing and writing grammatically correct recipes.

Introduction. Roman literature was created on the western shores of the Italian land in the language of one of the leading tribes of that time. Sources say that the spread of Latin was due to the expulsion of other languages from Roman territory, which dates back to the 4th-3rd centuries BC. As a result of the prosperity of the Roman Empire and the colonization of other peoples, this language spread throughout North Africa, Spain, Gaul, Germany and the Danube. It is well known that after the fall of the Roman Empire by the 5th century, there were territorial differences in the language of the peoples of the empire. The unity of written Latin was preserved, it continued to develop lexically, and the basic vocabulary and grammatical structure of classical Latin stabilized. In all areas where literary Latin was widely used, it also served as an administrative, commercial and written language. It was the language of diplomacy, science and philosophy until the 18th and 19th centuries. In the 20th century, the language of the Catholic Church became the official language of the Vatican. Latin, now known as a dead language, is the native language of the Romanian language group. Below we will look at the global status of this language. First of all, Latin is a medical language. All terms related to this field are studied in Latin. This language is widely taught in medical schools. The purpose of this course is to teach future medical professionals skills such as independent reading in Latin and understanding medical texts with the help of a dictionary, assimilation of information from scientific literature on the spot and writing in the specialty, diagnosis and writing grammatically correct prescriptions. In our speech, we often find words

that go back to Latin in their etymology. We forget that they are often confused with the vocabulary of our everyday life, and are absorbed into the living fabric of modern colloquial language and do not raise any doubt that they - these words - are rooted in our native language - so much have they managed to assimilate in it. Many of them have now become international words, such as constitution, conference, revolution, party, empire, republic, reform, congress, army, liberal, certification, institute, university, faculty, auditorium, lecture, consultation, professor, doctor of science, associate professor, auditor, student, laboratory, subject, object. There are some Latin expressions that do not even need to be translated, as they are familiar to our eyes. Examples include *Citius, Altius, Fortius* or *Alma Mater*, which call the place of spiritual nourishment an Olympic slogan. In addition, the literary expressions of one of the great Roman poets Horace *Aurea mediocritas* (Golden mean; Golden mean;) or *Carpe diem* (Take the chance; Seize the moment; *Fursatdan foydalan*), have their own alternatives in English, Russian and Uzbek; without translation, they are used in Romance languages, i.e. in the original. Because they are so common in everyday life that they are not felt by the languages of these peoples.

Roman literature is a rich cultural heritage for the peoples of the world. One of them is catchphrases, literary quotations, figurative expressions and proverbs. We know and are perfectly aware that the use of appropriate proverbs in our speech can add effect and eloquence to our speech. A proverb is cited in a number of scientific sources as a compact, figurative and witty phrase, usually created by people or a nation based on life experience. Each proverb is a sign of readiness, integrity and willingness to speak, and it is convincing and informative and is introduced into the language ready for use. They pass from generation to generation, enriching our speech: *Qui ne бедуть, не eat*; *Qui ne travaie pas, ne mange par (fr)*; *Who does not work, does not eat (rus)*;

Corvus corno oculos не eruit (nom)\ Dog does not eat dog; *Corbeaux contre corbeaux ne se cravent jamais les yeix (French)*; *A raven will not peck out a raven's eyes (Russian)*. *In angustiis amici apparent*; *A friend in need is a friend indeed*; *On connait l'ami dans le besoin (French)*; *Friends are known in trouble (Russian)*.

One of the means of figurative and expressive literary speech is winged words. This name goes back to Homer, in whose poems ("Iliad", "Odyssey") they occur many times. Homer called words "winged" because from the mouth of the speaker they seem to fly to the ear of the listener [2, p. 4]. Homer's expression "winged words" has become a term, and this term denotes short quotations, figurative expressions, sayings of historical figures and commanders, names of mythological and literary characters that have become household words (for example, *Hercules, Tartuffe, Achilles*) that have entered our speech from literary and mythical sources. In addition, meaningful expressions and winged words used by great thinkers occupy a worthy place in the languages of the peoples of the world. Winged words are phrases that are used in speech as a figurative illustrative quotation. It is well known that winged words differ in their aphorism, universality, meaning, ease of use and concreteness. These are expressions that convey deep thoughts in speech, which are expressive, figurative and briefly clarify the meaning of complex situations and characters, diverse in their origin. Many of them arose in distant eras and the cultures of different eras and countries enriched their stock. In a word, ancient and biblical myths, folk songs and fairy tales, world fiction,

criticism, journalism, memoirs, historical documents, scientific works, speeches of political and public figures are abundant sources of winged words and proverbs [2, p. 5].

As for winged words and expressions from Latin, it should be noted that winged words of Latin origin have their alternatives not only in new languages, but also in different language families, where their semantics are close to each other, and even in languages where race and religion are different and there they retain their winged charm and originality of meaning. For example, Dulce et decorum est pro patria mori (Horace); It is proud and exciting to breathe and live for motherland; Il est doux et beau mourir pour la patrie (French); It is gratifying and honorable to die for the fatherland (Russian). Salus populi suprema lex (Cicero); People's sake is the principle (eng); Que le salut du peuple soit la suprême loi (p); Let the good of the people be the supreme law (rus). Audaces fortuna juvat (Maron); Fortune favours the brave; La fortune favorise les audacieux (фр); Courage takes the city (rus).

As can be seen from the examples, Latin philosophical expressions have deep philosophical meanings, since they convey a sense of honor as a feeling of homeland, as well as great ideas, such as attention to man. It is polished in many languages.

Some of the proverbs or phrases that we use today in speech are also of Latin origin. It should be noted that the expressions that we use below are essentially expressions, catchphrases taken from the works of outstanding representatives - native speakers of the Latin language. It is safe to say that their meaning and expressive imagery were used as proverbs. Since a proverb is "an extremely laconic and at the same time surprisingly capacious and deeply meaningful genre of oral creativity, accumulated over many centuries on the basis of the socio-economic, political and cultural experience of the people" [5, p.5]. M.A. Sholokhov, for example, emphasizes the inexhaustibility of the treasury of folk proverbs that know no time boundaries: as if on wings they - proverbs - fly from century to century, from one generation to another, and that endless distance is not visible, where this winged wisdom directs its flight ... "[7, p.3]. O matra pulchra filia pulchrior (Horace); Good blood always shows itself; An apple doesn't fall far from the tree (Russian); Gutta cavat lapidem (Ovdiy); Little strokes fell great oaks; Drop by drop, and a stone will hollow (Russian); Ira auror brevis est (Horace); Anger is short madness; Gneve - short-term madness (Russian); Mens sana in corpora sano (Juvenal); An apple a day keeps the doctor away; A healthy mind in a healthy body (Russian); Potius sera, quam nunquam (Titus Livonia); It's better late than never; Better late than never (Russian); Veritas odium parit (Terence); Home truths are horrid to swallow, the truth hurts; The truth hurts the eyes (Russian); Est modus in rebus (Plautus); Everything is good in its season; Everything is good in moderation (Russian); Amor caecus (Plautus); Love is blind; Love is blind (Russian); Homo homini lupus est (Plautus); People's enemy is people; Man is a wolf to man (Russian); Amantium irae amoris integratio (Terence); Quarrel of lovers is renewing their love; Гнев Любимых - renewal of love (Russian).

This means that we can see the Latin language, now known as a dead language, in the works that have survived to this day. Thanks to these works, we see that Latin has developed and changed over the centuries. It is widely preserved in medieval historical monuments and documents, in the works of Renaissance figures. We see that among the peoples conquered by the Romans (Italians, Portuguese, French, Spaniards, Romanians), Latin played an important

role in the language process, its historical progress and evolution. This effect is manifested mainly due to the use of a large number of Latin words in their vocabulary.

Thus, various Latin terms, figurative expressions, proverbs and catchphrases really indicate the invaluable contribution of this language to the cultural-linguistic and spiritual progress of world civilization as one of the means of figurative and expressive literary and colloquial speech.

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